

STAKEHOLDERS' AWARENESS, ACCEPTANCE, and UNDERSTANDING of MinSU VISION, MISSION, FISHERIES EDUCATIONAL GOALS and OBJECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the awareness, acceptance, understanding, and perceptions of stakeholders regarding the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of Mindoro State University. The findings reveal that internal stakeholders, particularly administration and faculty, exhibit higher levels of awareness (mean score: 3.65) compared to external stakeholders such as parents and alumni (mean score: 3.52). Both groups demonstrate strong acceptance and understanding of the VMGO, with mean scores of 3.64 for acceptance and 3.61 for awareness of dissemination methods. However, discrepancies in awareness levels among external stakeholders highlight the need for targeted communication strategies, especially for linkages. Overall, the study emphasizes the importance of effective stakeholder engagement in fostering a shared understanding of the VMGO, which is crucial for aligning institutional practices with educational objectives and enhancing overall effectiveness.

Keywords: *Stakeholder Awareness, VMGO, Stakeholder Engagement, Acceptance and Understanding, Clarity and Consistency, Congruency with Practices,*

INTRODUCTION

Stakeholder awareness is crucial for effective management of fisheries programs, especially in academic settings like the Bachelor of Science in Fisheries program at Mindoro State University - Bongabong Campus. Recognizing the perceptions of stakeholders—including students, faculty, alumni, and industry partners—about the program's Vision, Mission, Institute of Fisheries Goals, and Program Objectives (VMGO) is vital for improving educational outcomes and meeting industry demands.

A well-defined VMGO framework is essential for success in higher education. These elements guide decision-making, shape institutional culture, and align stakeholder efforts toward common goals. Ordoñez (2015) states that a clear vision not only provides direction but also fosters ownership among stakeholders, which is critical for institutional development. The vision articulates aspirations, while the mission outlines actions needed to achieve those aspirations. This alignment is key to creating a cohesive educational environment where all members are motivated to contribute (Deazeley, 2015).

The goals and objectives of an academic program must be relevant to the needs of students, faculty, and the community. They serve as benchmarks for measuring program effectiveness and ensuring alignment with the mission and vision (IJSMS, 2019). By establishing clear objectives, the program can better prepare graduates for successful careers in the fisheries sector, enhancing its reputation and impact.

Accreditation also emphasizes the importance of VMGO in higher education. Bodies like the Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACCU) evaluate programs against quality standards. This process ensures that the program meets educational criteria and enhances its credibility within the academic community and among employers (CHED, 2006). Accreditation fosters continuous improvement and accountability within the institution.

Compliance with accrediting standards requires institutions to demonstrate how their VMGO are integrated into operations and educational practices. This alignment is essential for accreditation success, reflecting the institution's commitment to quality education and stakeholder needs (IJSMS, 2019). The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) notes that VMGO are fundamental to the accreditation process, serving as the basis for evaluating institutional performance (CHED, 2006).

Assessing stakeholder awareness of the VMGO of the Bachelor of Science in Fisheries program is essential for fostering effective engagement and improving outcomes. By understanding perceptions and addressing participation challenges, the program can enhance its relevance and responsiveness to the fisheries sector and the broader community. This study aims to provide insights that guide the development of targeted strategies for stakeholder engagement, contributing to the sustainability and success of the fisheries program at Mindoro State University - Bongabong Campus.

The significance of a well-defined VMGO for the Bachelor of Science in Fisheries program cannot be overstated. These elements guide the program's direction and decision-making and are crucial for achieving accreditation from bodies like AACCU. Ensuring that stakeholders are aware of and aligned with the VMGO can enhance the program's effectiveness, relevance, and overall success.

Research Objectives

1. To determine Awareness on the VMGO of Stakeholders
2. To determine Awareness on the VMGO of dissemination of Stakeholders
3. To assess the level of Acceptance and Understanding of Stakeholders to the VMGO
4. To evaluate Perceptions of Stakeholders regarding VMGO's clarity and consistency
5. To evaluate Perception of Stakeholders regarding VMGO's congruency with activities, practices, projects, and operations

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at the Mindoro State University - Bongabong Campus, specifically within the Institute of Fisheries. This setting provides a relevant context for examining the awareness and perceptions of stakeholders involved in the fisheries program. The researcher employed purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling technique where participants are selected based on specific characteristics relevant to the study (QuestionPro, 2024). This method allows for the inclusion of individuals who are most likely to provide valuable insights into the research questions.

The respondents for this study include both internal and external stakeholders of the Institute of Fisheries. Internal stakeholders comprise administrators, faculty members, non-teaching staff, and students enrolled in the second semester of the academic year 2023-2024 as shown in Figure 1. External stakeholders include parents, cooperating agencies, and alumni as presented in Figure 2. This group ensures a comprehensive understanding of stakeholder awareness and perceptions regarding the VMGO.

Figure 1. Internal Stakeholders

Figure 2. External Stakeholders

The study utilized a descriptive research method to gather quantitative data about stakeholder awareness. A modified version of a survey questionnaire developed in a recent study by Constantino (2020) is employed as the primary data collection instrument. The items related to VMGO are based on the criteria established by the Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACCU) in 2010. The survey instrument includes questions designed to measure the following aspects: Awareness of the VMGO among stakeholders; Awareness of the dissemination of the

VMGO; Level of acceptance and understanding of the VMGO; Perceptions regarding the clarity and consistency of the VMGO; and Perceptions of the congruency of the VMGO with activities, practices, projects, and operations

The researcher used a 4-point Likert scale to quantify responses, allowing participants to express their level of agreement or disagreement with each statement presented on Table 1 (Likert, 1932). Data collection was conducted online using Google Forms, facilitating easy access and participation. The study is limited to the Bachelor of Science in Fisheries program at Mindoro State University - Bongabong Campus. While it includes a variety of stakeholders, the findings may not be generalizable beyond this specific context. The focus on internal stakeholders (administrators, faculty, non-teaching staff, and students) and external stakeholders (parents, cooperating agencies, and alumni) provides a comprehensive view, yet the results may vary in different institutions or programs.

Table 1. Scaling and Quantification of Data

Mean	Awareness	Acceptance/Perception	Understanding
3.26 – 4.00	Highly Aware	Greatly Accept	Strongly Agree
2.51 – 3.25	Aware	Accept	Agree
1.76 – 2.50	Least Aware	Slightly Accept	Disagree
1.00 – 1.75	Not Aware	Not Accept	Strongly Disagree

RESULTS

Table 2. Awareness of the VMGO of Internal Stakeholders

Statements	Mean				Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Administration	Faculty	Non-teaching Staff	Students		
I am aware of the Vision of Mindoro State University.	3.65	3.56	3.43	3.66	3.58	Highly Aware
I am aware of the Mission of Mindoro State University	3.68	3.54	3.38	3.56	3.54	Highly Aware
I am aware of the Goal and Objectives of the programs offered.	3.64	3.62	3.31	3.70	3.57	Highly Aware
Overall	3.66	3.57	3.37	3.64	3.56	Highly Aware

The data presented in Table 2 indicates a high level of awareness among internal stakeholders regarding the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of Mindoro State University. The overall weighted mean score of 3.56, categorized as "Highly Aware," reflects a strong understanding across all groups, including administration, faculty, non-teaching staff, and students.

Table 3. Awareness of the VMGO of External Stakeholders

Statements	Mean			Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Parents/Guardians	Linkages	Alumni		
I am aware of the Vision of Mindoro State University.	3.49	3.26	3.58	3.44	Highly Aware
I am aware of the Mission of Mindoro State University	3.46	3.28	3.55	3.43	Highly Aware
I am aware of the Goal and Objectives of the programs offered.	3.50	3.33	3.46	3.43	Highly Aware
Overall	3.48	3.29	3.52	3.43	Highly Aware

The data presented in Table 3 illustrates the awareness of the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) among external stakeholders at Mindoro State University, specifically focusing on parents/guardians, linkages, and alumni. The overall weighted

mean score of 3.43, categorized as "Highly Aware," indicates a strong level of awareness across these groups.

Table 4. Awareness of Internal Stakeholders on the Dissemination of VMGO

Statements	Mean				Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Administration	Faculty	Non-teaching Staff	Students		
I am aware that the VMGO are displayed on bulletin boards.	3.78	3.76	3.64	3.81	3.75	Highly Aware
I am aware that VMGO is printed in catalogs, manuals and other materials.	3.76	3.77	3.58	3.77	3.72	Highly Aware
I am aware that the VMGO is broadcasted in media and/or internet/website.	3.79	3.67	3.55	3.84	3.71	Highly Aware
I am aware that the VMGO is widely disseminated to the different agencies, institutions, industry sectors, and the community as a whole.	3.61	3.57	3.56	3.79	3.63	Highly Aware
Overall	3.74	3.69	3.58	3.80	3.70	Highly Aware

The data presented in the table reflects the awareness of internal stakeholders regarding the dissemination of the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of Mindoro State University. The overall weighted mean score of 3.70, categorized as "Highly Aware," indicates a strong understanding among stakeholders about how the VMGO is communicated throughout the university and beyond.

Table 5. Awareness of External Stakeholders on the Dissemination of VMGO

Statements	Mean			Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Parents/Guardians	Linkages	Alumni		
I am aware that the VMGO are displayed on bulletin boards.	3.64	3.28	3.77	3.56	Highly Aware
I am aware that VMGO is printed in catalogs, manuals and other materials.	3.67	3.26	3.68	3.54	Highly Aware
I am aware that the VMGO is broadcasted in media and/or internet/website.	3.43	3.33	3.69	3.48	Highly Aware
I am aware that the VMGO is widely disseminated to the different agencies, institutions, industry sectors, and the community as a whole.	3.33	3.30	3.72	3.45	Highly Aware
Overall	3.52	3.29	3.72	3.51	Highly Aware

The data presented in the table reflects the awareness of external stakeholders regarding the dissemination of the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of Mindoro State University. The overall weighted mean score of 3.51, categorized as "Highly Aware," indicates a generally strong understanding among these stakeholders about how the VMGO is communicated to them and the broader community.

Table 6. Acceptance and Understanding Internal Stakeholders to the VMGO

Statements	Mean				Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Administration	Faculty	Non-teaching Staff	Students		
I accept and understand the Vision and Mission of Mindoro State University.	3.84	3.78	3.64	3.79	3.76	Highly Aware

I accept and understand of Goals of the Institute of Fisheries of Mindoro State University.	3.80	3.76	3.61	3.77	3.74	Highly Aware
I accept and understand the Objectives of the program where I belong and the responsibility of realizing such objectives in my capacity.	3.81	3.81	3.66	3.76	3.76	Highly Aware
Overall	3.82	3.78	3.64	3.77	3.75	Highly Aware

The data presented in Table 6 reflects the acceptance and understanding of internal stakeholders regarding the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of Mindoro State University. The overall weighted mean score of 3.75, categorized as "Highly Aware," indicates that stakeholders have a strong acceptance and understanding of the university's VMGO.

Table 7. Acceptance and Understanding External Stakeholders to the VMGO

Statements	Mean			Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Parents/Guardians	Linkages	Alumni		
I accept and understand the Vision and Mission of Mindoro State University.	3.56	3.34	3.72	3.54	Highly Aware
I accept and understand of Goals of the Institute of Fisheries of Mindoro State University.	3.49	3.36	3.70	3.52	Highly Aware
I accept and understand the Objectives of the program where I belong and the responsibility of realizing such objectives in my capacity.	3.44	3.41	3.74	3.53	Highly Aware
Overall	3.50	3.37	3.72	3.53	Highly Aware

The data presented in the table reflects the acceptance and understanding of external stakeholders regarding the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of Mindoro State University. The overall weighted mean score of 3.53, categorized as "Highly Aware," indicates a strong level of acceptance and understanding among these stakeholders.

Table 8. Perceptions of Internal Stakeholders regarding VMGO's clarity and consistency

Statements	Mean				Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Administration	Faculty	Non-teaching Staff	Students		
The vision reflects what Mindoro State University hopes to become in the future.	3.67	3.78	3.32	3.78	3.64	Highly Aware
The mission reflects Mindoro State University legal and educational mandate.	3.59	3.46	3.34	3.64	3.51	Highly Aware
The goals of the institute programs are clearly stated and are consistent with the mission of Mindoro State University.	3.44	3.55	3.31	3.61	3.48	Highly Aware
The program objectives are consistent with the goals of Institute of Fisheries of Mindoro State University.	3.57	3.43	3.34	3.44	3.45	Highly Aware
The program objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of	3.51	3.47	3.56	3.58	3.53	Highly Aware

competencies or technical skills of students and graduates.						
The program objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of research and extension capabilities of students and graduates.	3.68	3.56	3.61	3.67	3.63	Highly Aware
The program objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of students' ideas, desirable attitudes, and personal discipline.	3.55	3.51	3.41	3.46	3.48	Highly Aware
The program objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of moral character.	3.77	3.77	3.49	3.54	3.64	Highly Aware
The program objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of critical thinking skills.	3.46	3.63	3.46	3.69	3.56	Highly Aware
The program objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of aesthetic and cultural values.	3.67	3.48	3.50	3.33	3.50	Highly Aware
Overall	3.59	3.56	3.43	3.58	3.54	Highly Aware

The data presented in the table reflects the acceptance and understanding of internal stakeholders regarding the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of Mindoro State University. The overall weighted mean score of 3.54, categorized as "Highly Aware," indicates a strong level of acceptance and understanding among these stakeholders.

Table 9. Perceptions of External Stakeholders regarding VMGO's clarity and consistency

Statements	Mean			Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Parents/Guardians	Linkages	Alumni		
The vision reflects what Mindoro State University hopes to become in the future.	3.64	3.34	3.71	3.56	Highly Aware
The mission reflects Mindoro State University legal and educational mandate.	3.63	3.54	3.79	3.65	Highly Aware
The goals of the institute programs are clearly stated and are consistent with the mission of Mindoro State University.	3.70	3.36	3.64	3.57	Highly Aware
The program objectives are consistent with the goals of Institute of Fisheries of Mindoro State University.	3.52	3.40	3.71	3.54	Highly Aware
The program objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of competencies or technical skills of students and graduates.	3.64	3.41	3.55	3.53	Highly Aware
The program objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of research and extension capabilities of students and graduates.	3.51	3.46	3.57	3.51	Highly Aware
The program objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of students' ideas, desirable attitudes, and personal discipline.	3.49	3.29	3.34	3.35	Highly Aware

The program objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of moral character.	3.69	3.33	3.47	3.50	Highly Aware
The program objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of critical thinking skills.	3.70	3.40	3.36	3.49	Highly Aware
The program objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of aesthetic and cultural values.	3.54	3.37	3.44	3.42	Highly Aware
Overall	3.61	3.39	3.56	3.42	Highly Aware

The data presented in the table reflects the acceptance and understanding of external stakeholders regarding the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of Mindoro State University. The overall weighted mean score of 3.54, categorized as "Highly Aware," indicates a strong level of acceptance and understanding among these stakeholders.

Table 10. Perception of Internal Stakeholders regarding VMGO's congruency with activities, practices, projects, and operations

Statements	Mean				Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Administration	Faculty	Non-teaching Staff	Students		
There is congruency between actual practices and activities and the mission of Mindoro State University.	3.78	3.76	3.34	3.70	3.65	Highly Aware
There is congruency between actual educational practices and activities and the goals of the University.	3.71	3.67	3.40	3.76	3.64	Highly Aware
There is congruency between actual educational practices and activities and the objectives of the program where I belong.	3.69	3.58	3.45	3.68	3.60	Highly Aware
The projects and activities carried out by the faculty and students directly contribute towards the achievement of the program outcomes.	3.75	3.72	3.38	3.74	3.65	Highly Aware
The VMGO is the basis of all Mindoro State University operations.	3.72	3.70	3.50	3.72	3.66	Highly Aware
Overall	3.73	3.69	3.41	3.72	3.64	Highly Aware

The data presented in the table reflects the perception of external stakeholders regarding the congruency between the actual practices and activities at Mindoro State University and its Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO). The overall weighted mean score of 3.64, categorized as "Highly Aware," indicates a strong recognition among stakeholders that the university's operations align well with its stated objectives.

Table 11. Perception of External Stakeholders regarding VMGO's congruency with activities, practices, projects, and operations

Statements	Mean			Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Parents/Guardians	Linkages	Alumni		
There is congruency between actual between practices and activities and the mission of Mindoro State University.	3.67	3.45	3.70	3.61	Highly Aware
There is congruency between actual educational practices and	3.45	3.40	3.68	3.51	Highly Aware

activities and the goals of the University.					
There is congruency between actual educational practices and activities and the objectives of the program where I belong.	3.54	3.56	3.71	3.60	Highly Aware
The projects and activities carried out by the faculty and students directly contribute towards the achievement of the program outcomes.	3.63	3.50	3.69	3.61	Highly Aware
The VMGO is the basis of all Mindoro State University operations.	3.70	3.66	3.66	3.67	Highly Aware
Overall	3.60	3.51	3.69	3.60	Highly Aware

The data presented in the table reflects the perception of external stakeholders regarding the congruency between actual practices and activities at Mindoro State University and its Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO). The overall weighted mean score of 3.60, categorized as "Highly Aware," indicates a strong recognition among stakeholders that the university's operations align well with its stated objectives.

Table 12. Summary of stakeholders' awareness, acceptance, understanding, and perceptions of Mindoro State University VMGO.

Statements	Mean		Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Internal Stakeholder	External Stakeholder		
Awareness on the VMGO	3.64	3.52	3.58	Highly Aware
Awareness on the VMGO of dissemination	3.70	3.51	3.61	Highly Aware
Acceptance and understanding of the stakeholders to the VMGO	3.75	3.53	3.64	Highly Aware
Perceptions of stakeholders regarding VMGOs clarity and consistency	3.54	3.42	3.48	Highly Aware
Perception of Stakeholders regarding VMGOs congruency with activities, practices, projects and operations	3.64	3.60	3.62	Highly Aware
Overall	3.65	3.52	3.59	Highly Aware

The data presented in the table reflects the awareness, acceptance, and understanding of both internal and external stakeholders regarding the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of Mindoro State University. The overall weighted mean score of 3.59, categorized as "Highly Aware," indicates that stakeholders generally recognize and accept the VMGO.

DISCUSSION

Awareness of the VMGO of Internal Stakeholders

Administration members reported the highest awareness of the university's mission with a mean score of 3.68, while non-teaching staff had the lowest awareness regarding the goals and objectives at 3.31. This discrepancy suggests that while administrative staff are well-informed about the VMGO, there is a need for improved communication strategies targeting non-teaching staff to enhance their understanding.

Research supports the notion that stakeholder awareness is essential for effective organizational functioning. For instance, Mackinson et al. (2010) emphasize that stakeholder engagement improves governance and management decisions in educational settings, leading to better alignment with institutional goals. Similarly, Pita et al. (2010) argue that understanding stakeholder perceptions can significantly influence the outcomes of management initiatives. Therefore, enhancing awareness among all internal stakeholders is critical for fostering a cohesive educational environment where everyone is aligned with the university's objectives.

Moreover, students exhibited strong awareness of both the vision and goals, scoring 3.66 and 3.70, respectively. This suggests that students are actively engaged with the university's mission and objectives, which is crucial for their academic success and overall satisfaction with their educational experience (Deazeley, 2015). However, to maintain this engagement and ensure continuous improvement in stakeholder awareness, targeted outreach efforts should be implemented.

Awareness of the VMGO of External Stakeholders

Parents/guardians reported a mean score of 3.49 for awareness of the university's vision, while alumni showed slightly higher awareness with a score of 3.58. Linkages had the lowest mean score at 3.26, suggesting that this group may need more targeted communication regarding the VMGO.

The findings suggest that while external stakeholders generally exhibit high awareness of the VMGO, there are notable differences among groups. For instance, alumni demonstrate a solid understanding of the university's mission (mean score of 3.55) and goals (mean score of 3.46), which aligns with research indicating that engaged alumni often have better awareness of institutional objectives. In contrast, parents/guardians show slightly lower scores for both the mission (3.46) and goals (3.50), indicating that they may require more information to fully understand these aspects.

Moreover, the study by Atwere et al. (2023) emphasizes the importance of stakeholder engagement in research and guideline development, highlighting that effective engagement can improve transparency and trust among stakeholders. This research found that clearly defining roles and levels of engagement can enhance stakeholder participation, which is critical for fostering a supportive environment around institutional objectives. Therefore, addressing gaps in awareness among linkages and parents can lead to stronger support for the university's initiatives and goals.

Awareness of Internal Stakeholders on the Dissemination of VMGO

Notably, the highest mean score is observed for awareness of VMGO displayed on bulletin boards, with an overall mean of 3.75. This suggests that stakeholders, particularly students (mean score of 3.81) and administration (mean score of 3.78), are well-informed about the visibility of the VMGO within the campus environment.

Awareness regarding printed materials such as catalogs and manuals also demonstrates a strong understanding, with an overall mean score of 3.72. All groups exhibit similar levels of awareness, particularly faculty members who scored 3.77, indicating that printed communication effectively reaches stakeholders. Furthermore, the statement regarding broadcasting the VMGO through media and online platforms received a mean score of 3.71, reflecting high awareness across all groups, with students reporting the highest awareness at 3.84. This suggests that digital communication channels are effectively engaging this demographic.

However, the lowest mean score was recorded for the statement about VMGO being disseminated to various agencies and community sectors, with an overall mean of

3.63. While still categorized as "Highly Aware," this indicates that there may be opportunities to enhance outreach efforts to ensure that external stakeholders are equally informed about the VMGO. Research by Forsythe et al. (2018) emphasizes that effective stakeholder engagement improves research relevance and fosters mutual understanding between stakeholders and researchers, which can significantly impact institutional success.

Awareness of External Stakeholders on the Dissemination of VMGO

Notably, the highest mean score is recorded for awareness of VMGO displayed on bulletin boards, with an overall mean of 3.56. This suggests that parents/guardians (mean score of 3.64) and alumni (mean score of 3.77) are relatively well-informed about the visibility of the VMGO within the university environment, while linkages reported a lower score (3.28), indicating a need for improved communication with this group.

Awareness regarding VMGO being printed in catalogs, manuals, and other materials shows a similar trend, with an overall mean score of 3.54. Parents/guardians had a mean score of 3.67, suggesting effective communication through printed materials, while linkages again reported the lowest awareness at 3.26. Furthermore, the statement regarding broadcasting the VMGO through media and online platforms received a mean score of 3.48, reflecting moderate awareness across all groups. Parents/guardians had the lowest awareness in this category with a score of 3.43, while alumni had higher awareness at 3.69, suggesting that digital communication channels are more effective for engaging this demographic.

However, the lowest mean score was recorded for the statement about VMGO being disseminated to various agencies and community sectors, with an overall mean of 3.45. While still categorized as "Highly Aware," this indicates that there may be opportunities to enhance outreach efforts to ensure that all external stakeholders are adequately informed about the VMGO. Research by Sattar et al. (2022) emphasizes that stakeholder participation is crucial for improving educational outcomes and fostering a supportive environment around institutional objectives. Their study highlights that active engagement leads to better alignment between educational goals and stakeholder expectations, ultimately enhancing institutional effectiveness.

Acceptance and Understanding Internal Stakeholders to the VMGO

Notably, the highest mean score is recorded for the statement regarding acceptance and understanding of the Vision and Mission, with a mean of 3.76. This suggests that stakeholders, particularly administration (mean score of 3.84) and faculty (mean score of 3.78), are well-informed about these fundamental elements of the university's framework.

Furthermore, awareness regarding the Goals of the Institute of Fisheries also shows a high level of acceptance, with an overall mean score of 3.74. This indicates that internal stakeholders recognize the importance of these goals in guiding their responsibilities within the institution. The statement regarding acceptance and understanding of program objectives received a mean score of 3.76, which further emphasizes that stakeholders are not only aware but also feel a sense of responsibility towards realizing these objectives in their respective capacities.

Research by Mamo Haile and Mekonnen (2024) supports these findings by highlighting that stakeholder engagement is crucial for effective curriculum implementation and institutional success. Their study found that when stakeholders accept and understand institutional goals, they are more likely to participate actively in achieving them, thereby enhancing overall educational outcomes. This aligns with the

results from Mindoro State University, where high levels of acceptance among internal stakeholders can lead to better alignment with institutional objectives.

Acceptance and Understanding External Stakeholders to the VMGO

The highest mean score is recorded for the statement regarding acceptance and understanding of the VMGO, with a mean of 3.56 for parents/guardians and 3.72 for alumni. This suggests that these groups are relatively well-informed about the university's framework, while linkages reported a lower score (3.34), indicating a need for improved communication with this group.

Awareness regarding the Goals of the Institute of Fisheries also shows a high level of acceptance, with an overall mean score of 3.52. This indicates that external stakeholders recognize the importance of these goals in guiding their responsibilities within the institution. The statement regarding acceptance and understanding of program objectives received a mean score of 3.53, further emphasizing that stakeholders not only accept but also feel a sense of responsibility toward realizing these objectives.

Research by Ferrero-Ferrero et al. (2018) supports these findings by highlighting that effective stakeholder engagement is crucial for aligning institutional goals with stakeholder expectations. Their study found that when stakeholders understand and accept institutional objectives, they are more likely to participate actively in achieving them, thereby enhancing overall institutional effectiveness. This aligns with the results from Mindoro State University, where high levels of acceptance among external stakeholders can lead to better alignment with institutional objectives.

Perceptions of Internal Stakeholders regarding VMGO's clarity and consistency

Notably, the highest mean score is recorded for the statement regarding the vision reflecting what Mindoro State University hopes to become in the future, with a mean of 3.64. This suggests that stakeholders, particularly faculty (mean score of 3.78) and administration (mean score of 3.67), are well-informed about the university's aspirations.

Awareness regarding the mission reflecting Mindoro State University's legal and educational mandate also shows a high level of acceptance, with an overall mean score of 3.51. This indicates that stakeholders recognize the mission's importance in guiding institutional operations. The goals of the institute programs received a mean score of 3.48, suggesting that stakeholders perceive these goals as clearly stated and aligned with the university's mission.

Research by Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka (2015) supports these findings by emphasizing that stakeholder understanding of an institution's VMGO is crucial for effective engagement and alignment with institutional objectives. Their study highlights that when stakeholders accept and understand these foundational elements, they are more likely to contribute positively to achieving the institution's goals, enhancing overall effectiveness.

Perceptions of External Stakeholders regarding VMGO's clarity and consistency

the highest mean score is recorded for the statement regarding the vision reflecting what Mindoro State University hopes to become in the future, with a mean of 3.64 for parents/guardians and 3.71 for alumni. This suggests that these groups are relatively well-informed about the university's aspirations, while linkages reported a lower score (3.34), indicating a need for improved communication with this group.

Awareness regarding the mission reflecting Mindoro State University's legal and educational mandate also shows a high level of acceptance, with an overall mean score

of 3.65. This indicates that stakeholders recognize the mission's importance in guiding institutional operations. The goals of the institute programs received a mean score of 3.57, suggesting that stakeholders perceive these goals as clearly stated and aligned with the university's mission.

Research by Mamo Haile et al. (2022) supports these findings by emphasizing that stakeholder engagement is essential for achieving institutional objectives and fostering a sense of ownership among stakeholders. Their study found that when stakeholders understand and accept institutional goals, they are more likely to actively participate in achieving them, thereby enhancing overall effectiveness. This aligns with the results from Mindoro State University, where high levels of acceptance among external stakeholders can lead to better alignment with institutional objectives.

Perception of Internal Stakeholders regarding VMGO's congruency with activities, practices, projects, and operations

Notably, the highest mean score is recorded for the statement regarding congruency between actual practices and activities and the mission of Mindoro State University, with a mean of 3.65. This suggests that stakeholders, particularly administration (mean score of 3.78) and faculty (mean score of 3.76), perceive a strong alignment between the university's mission and its day-to-day operations.

Awareness regarding congruency between educational practices and the university's goals also shows a high level of acceptance, with an overall mean score of 3.64. This indicates that stakeholders recognize the importance of these goals in guiding their responsibilities within the institution. Furthermore, stakeholders believe that the projects and activities carried out by faculty and students contribute directly to achieving program outcomes, as reflected in the mean score of 3.65.

Research by Bess and Dee (2012) supports these findings by emphasizing that alignment between institutional practices and stated goals is crucial for fostering a cohesive educational environment. Their study highlights that when stakeholders perceive congruency in an institution's operations, it enhances their commitment to achieving shared objectives and promotes a culture of accountability within the institution.

Perception of External Stakeholders regarding VMGO's congruency with activities, practices, projects, and operations

The highest mean score is recorded for the statement regarding congruency between actual practices and activities and the mission of Mindoro State University, with a mean of 3.67 for parents/guardians and 3.70 for alumni. This suggests that these groups perceive a solid alignment between the university's mission and its daily operations, while linkages reported a lower score (3.45), indicating a need for improved communication with this group.

Awareness regarding congruency between educational practices and the university's goals also shows a high level of acceptance, with an overall mean score of 3.51. This indicates that stakeholders recognize the importance of these goals in guiding their responsibilities within the institution. Furthermore, stakeholders believe that the projects and activities carried out by faculty and students contribute directly to achieving program outcomes, as reflected in the mean score of 3.61.

Research by Makhdoom et al. (2021) supports these findings by emphasizing that alignment between institutional practices and stated goals is crucial for fostering a cohesive educational environment. Their study highlights that when stakeholders perceive congruency in an institution's operations, it enhances their commitment to achieving shared objectives and promotes a culture of accountability within the institution.

Summary of stakeholders' awareness, acceptance, understanding, and perceptions of Isabela State University VMGO

Internal stakeholders reported a higher mean score of 3.65 compared to external stakeholders, who had a mean score of 3.52. This suggests that internal stakeholders, such as faculty and administration, are more familiar with and engaged in the VMGO than external stakeholders like parents and alumni.

The highest mean score was recorded for awareness of the VMGO dissemination at 3.61, indicating that both groups acknowledge the importance of effectively communicating these objectives. Additionally, the acceptance and understanding of the VMGO were also high, with an overall mean score of 3.64. This reflects a strong commitment among stakeholders to align their actions with the university's mission and goals.

Research by Castro et al. (2017) supports these findings by emphasizing that stakeholder engagement is critical for fostering a shared understanding of an institution's VMGO. Their study found that when institutions actively involve stakeholders in discussions about their vision and mission, it enhances awareness and acceptance across all groups. This aligns with the results from Mindoro State University, where internal stakeholders demonstrate a higher level of engagement compared to external stakeholders.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Both internal and external stakeholders exhibit high levels of awareness regarding the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of Mindoro State University, with internal stakeholders showing slightly higher awareness scores.
2. Stakeholders are well-informed about the dissemination of the VMGO through various channels, including bulletin boards and printed materials.
3. A strong level of acceptance and understanding of the VMGO among stakeholders, particularly among internal groups such as administration and faculty.
4. Stakeholders perceive the VMGO as clear and consistent, with high mean scores indicating that they understand how these elements guide institutional practices.
5. Stakeholders perceive a strong congruency between the university's VMGO and its actual practices, projects, and operations.

Recommendations

In light of the findings, the following suggestions are presented below for consideration:

1. Develop initiatives aimed at non-teaching staff to improve their awareness and understanding of the VMGO.
2. Implement programs for external stakeholders, particularly linkages and parents/guardians, to enhance their awareness of the VMGO.
3. Encourage active participation from all stakeholder groups in discussions about the VMGO through forums or focus groups.
4. Conduct periodic surveys to evaluate stakeholders' perceptions regarding the clarity and consistency of the VMGO.
5. Ensure that all activities, projects, and operations within the university are consistently aligned with the VMGO.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations were paramount in conducting this study. Participants were informed about the purpose of the research and assured that their involvement was voluntary. No participant was forced to partake in the study, and they were free to withdraw at any time without any consequences. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, ensuring that their rights and privacy were respected throughout the research process.

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